

**THE CURRENT IMPORTANCE AND TASK OF LEARNING FOREIGN
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ANNOTATION: This article discusses the importance of teaching foreign languages and the state of its foreign language teaching materials today. In this way, along with interactive methods, traditional teaching methods are compared and clear conclusions are given. Additionally, traditional interactive teaching methods, considered useful in learning additional languages, are intended to achieve effective results in teaching foreign languages in four aspects (reading, listening, writing, and speaking skills).

Keywords: interactive tasks, didactic systematization, educational function, CEFR, IELTS, PIRLS, PISA.

Nowadays, great importance is attached to learning and teaching foreign languages. The Presidential Resolution, adopted on December 10 2012, on measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages expanded the ability to learn foreign languages. New methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of European countries (CEFR, IELTS, PIRLS, PISA) for the teaching of a foreign language and the evaluation of the knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. According to him, textbooks and teaching materials are being created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges.

The demand for foreign language learning is also increasing day by day. Foreign languages are divided into four aspects (reading, age, listening, understanding, and speaking), each of which provides special concepts, skills, and skills. Educational technologies mean the unforgettable use of modern information technology in teaching. It also envisions improving the quality and effectiveness of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the teaching process. In particular, there are several advantages to the use of such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. Currently, the modern approach to learning and teaching the language is insignificant. The use of technological tools is further used in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, writing, listening, understanding, and

speaking). For example, for listening and understanding, this process is certainly not possible without computers, players, CD discs. Listening and understanding is one of the most important parts of language learning. At one point, the reader is required to pay attention to the pronunciation of the speaker, his adherence to grammatical rules, his vocabulary, and his meanings. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective methods, and it is also intended to use it in a combination of interactive tasks with a communicative approach. [2.36-37] In this process, including:

- when using computers, the reader can also hear foreign-language video clips, demonstrations, dialogues, movies, or movies, but also learn to imitate them; - the ability to hear and watch foreign-language radio broadcasts and television programs;

- to have a large language learning base using smartphones and social networks, which are considered a traditional method;

- CD players can be used. Using these technical tools will make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective, as well as ensuring that students' attention is concentrated in one place in the classroom [1]. It is well-known that the lesson is based on a variety of games that will help students to demonstrate their hidden abilities by expanding their abilities, focusing, improving their knowledge and skills, and being strong. A teaching style consisting of a combination of play games and exercises aimed at finding solutions to problematic situations will prevent students from being distracted during the course, producing them with the ability to find solutions to the problem and conduct independent research. Psychologists say that the psychological mechanisms of moving games rely on the fundamental needs of an individual to manifest himself, find a stable place in life, self-government, and realize his or her capabilities. Generally accepted teaching principles, tactics must lie at the time of any game.

Interactive training is now used mainly in interactive ways. In the future, these methods will be harmonized to some extent with interactive technology. This is how we think the difference between the interfaith method and the concepts of technology can be described. The interfaith method of teaching is carried out by each teacher at the level of the tools available and at their own level. At the same time, each reader adapts to varying degrees in accordance with his motivations and intellectual level. Interfaith teaching technology ensures that each teacher conducts an exercise that all students master as intended.

Based on a study of some experiences in the application of interfaith activities, we may indicate some factors that affect the quality and effectiveness of these exercises. They can be

conditionally referred to as organizational-pedagogical, scientific, methodological, and factors related to teachers, students, and teaching tools. We should consider whether they, in their essence, have a positive or negative effect. Organizational and pedagogical factors include the preparation of a group of trainers conducting interactive classes from teachers;

- organize the teaching of interactive methods to teachers;
- create the necessary conditions for interactive training in the classroom;
- ensure that the workplace of the speaker and participants is convenient; - prevention of violations of sanitary and hygienic norms;
- ensuring compliance with safety regulations;
- maintaining health and discipline; — organizing supervision, etc.

Scientific and methodological factors include:

-Correct selection of interactive methods intended to ensure the fulfillment of DTS requirements and the full achievement of the objectives of the lesson;

- quality training of interfaith training;
- ensure that each element of interactive exercise is related to the subject being studied;
- determine the subject and content of the exercises based on the latest scientific and theoretical information;
- the use of modern high-performance methods;
- preliminarily determine the level of preparation of students and conduct appropriate interactive classes;

- to be able to take enough time for interfaith training, etc. During interfaith classes, a lot more creativity and activity is required from the teacher. [1.144] The lesson in the form of a narrative of what you read from a previously known or book that requires much more creativity and activity passes passively. The interfaith method works especially well not only in education but also in discipline, not only when a teacher influences discussion from a scientific point of view, but also expresses his or her personal attitude, moral position, and worldview of the problem. Teacher participation in student debates may vary. But in any case, he should not pass on his mind. Best of all, a well-calculated method of managing an argument should be managed by putting a question that requires generous thinking, creative research in finding a solution, or by putting a problematic question. The teacher has an opinion on how to draw conclusions from his point of view, only by drawing conclusions from the opinions of students and rejecting erroneous opinions. In this way, not only can the content of the debate be intellectual - knowledge, theoretical questions, but also the development of productive activities in

cooperation and the impact of students' personality on learning. [2.87] In this order, the method of interactive teaching, the cooperation of students, will not only make the learning process a collaborative activity due to the teacher's participation in the debates, but will become a real creative activity of a person's social relationship.

It should be noted that student and teacher friendly cooperation is also a unique teaching approach today, and a strict criticism of the teacher is also carried out in a mildly encouraging way. When it comes to systematising interactive assignments as a young researcher, I can suggest that today's youth differ from yesterday's generation in their ability to use their strong knowledge, especially electronic technologies. In the meantime, not only the use of interactive games but also intelligent, well-educated teaching becomes a pressing issue of the day. [3.90] Therefore, keeping the attention of the generations of the 21st century together and organizing an interesting lesson requires the teacher's ability to be skilled and skilled, to be strongly knowledgeable, to be sought after. I would propose a combination of traditional methods and innovative methods for creating and using an interactive task system, in which active members of the learning process play a key role, mainly as a manifestation of the new learning process. To assist individuals desiring to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a brochure entitled "Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide" has been prepared. Working on a project (project work) encourages the student's creative ability, thinking to create innovation, creating a competitive environment. [4.89] Choosing exercises (activity) integrated into one another, including reading, writing, espressos, and speaking the 4 main aspects of a foreign language, also guarantees effective teaching. For example, the reading aspect of grammar and vocabulary is interconnected with the writing aspect, and with the help of torches conducted in the development of the reading aspect, a child's vocabulary, and writing skills develop together. [1.77] For example: Filling in gaps, finding headline exercises increases the student's critical thinking while also increasing his or her vocabulary. Currently, teachers are using the following innovative methods, relying on the experience of the United States Stats, English teachers: [2.98]

- Solution to the problem (Creative Problem Solving) to use this method, the beginning of the story will be read, and the end will be attributed to the judgment of students and students;
- Cheerful riddles (Merry Riddles) teaching students riddles is important in teaching English, they learn words that are unfamiliar to them and find the answer to the riddle;
- Quick answer (Quick answers) will help improve the effectiveness of the lesson;
- Confused wrote (Warm-up exercises) use all kinds of games in the classroom to interest

students in the classroom [3.58];

- Pantomime (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson or in writing, where very difficult topics should be explained, and students are tired;

- The story chain (a chain story) method helps students grow their oral discourse;

- Role games (Acting characters) this method can be used in all types of lessons.

To teach craftsmanship, professionals such as Interpreter, Translator, Writer, Poet can participate in the lesson and talk to the students; A meeting of allies (Thinkers meeting) can invite poets and writers such as U.S. Shakespeare, R Burns. Using the words of wisdom they have spoken in the classroom at this time will help young people to be raised perfect people;

- When you speak pictures (When pictures speak) method is much more convenient and helps to teach English, to develop the oral discourse of students and students, using pictures related to the topic;

- Quiz cards (quiz cards) cards are distributed depending on the number of students and allow all students to participate in the classroom at the same time, which saves time [4]. At the end of the lesson objective explanation at the end of the lesson, students will present the knowledge they have learned in the classroom in the style or writing they want.

- Last impression finally the lesson will be obtained from the students as a questionnaire, in accordance with their interests, which they want to learn in the next lesson. As we have seen, every innovative technology has its own advantages. All such methods include cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active movement of the student in the teaching process [3.67].

In conclusion, the use of innovative methods in English will result in the development of students' ability to think logically, improve their speech, and develop the ability to respond quickly and accurately. Such methods stimulate a student's appetite for knowledge. Additionally, at the beginning of the lesson, visual, moving or role-playing in the middle of the lesson, and in the last part of the lesson, integrating the subjective opinions of the student about the information he or she learned in the classroom in various cartridges or anonymous games will not only interest the learner in learning the language but also stimulate the learner psychologically and improve the quality of education. The reader strives to prepare carefully for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the learning process. As the education system makes it a task to educate a free thinker, perfect, mature person, in the future, we can contribute to the development of future teachers more perfectly ways to make the most of innovative technologies and interfaith methods.

References:

1. M. Kholdorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rixsittilayeva. Use auxiliary tools to teach a foreign language. Tashkent: TDPU named Nizamiy, 2005
2. Ambrose, S., Bridges, M., Lovett, M., DiPietro, M., & Norman, M. (2010). How learning works: 7 research-based principles for smart teaching. San Francisco, CA: Jossey Bass.
3. Bekmuratova U.B. Use innovative technologies to teach English. Tashkent - 2012
4. N.Q. Khatamova, M.N. Mirzayeva. Interfaith methods used in English (Style Manual), Nebuchadnezzar, 2006, page 40.